

Ageing Europe: Demographic Change, Active Ageing, and EU Legislative Strategies¹

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Abstract

Population ageing represents one of the most significant demographic and socio-economic challenges currently facing the European Union. Driven primarily by declining fertility rates and increasing life expectancy, this process has profound implications for labour markets, pension systems, public finances, and social cohesion. The study aims to analyse population ageing within the European Union, with a particular focus on the social position of older persons and the extent to which European Union legislation and strategic initiatives address their needs. Using a three-stage methodological approach—comprising a review of demographic theory and contemporary research, an analysis of demographic ageing trends in the EU, and an examination of selected EU legislative and strategic measures—the article explores key issues related to active ageing, equal treatment, labour market participation, and the coordination of social security systems. Special attention is devoted to anti-discrimination law, notably Council Directive 2000/78/EC, related case law of the Court of Justice of the European Union, and non-legislative initiatives such as the Green Paper on Ageing. The findings highlight both progress and persisting gaps in EU-level responses, underlining the need for more comprehensive and binding legislative action to improve the quality of life and social inclusion of older persons.

KEY WORDS: population ageing, European Union, active ageing, demographic change, social and labour policy

INTRODUCTION

The countries of the European Union are facing various problems caused by an ageing population, which are related to many aspects of the economy, such as economic globalisation, international trade, economic growth, the workforce, building a pension system, protecting the rights of older people, capital accumulation and, of course, savings. Demographic change is thus currently a major political challenge, particularly in developed countries. In the case of EU countries, a larger older population is driven by increasing life expectancy and declining birth rates. However, longer life expectancy should increase savings if middle-aged individuals change their behaviour to increase savings in response to higher life expectancy. In effect, policymakers should thus encourage households to save for expected developments in later life, including health care costs. (Pascual-Saez, et al., 2020)

Our study focuses on the population of the European Union, accentuating the view on the position of the elderly and the improvement of their position in society. The main objective of the article is to investigate the aging of the population and to assess the possibilities of risks and

¹ This paper is the result of Metropolitan University Prague research project no. 116-3 “International Relations and Territorial Studies” (2025) based on a grant from the Institutional Fund for the Long-term Strategic Development of Research Organizations

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dilemmas of demographic aging in the space of the European Union countries in the context of selected legislative strategic actions of the European Union in relation to the elderly.

There are pressing issues related to the growing elderly population. These include above all the coordination of social security systems within the framework of the free movement of persons within the EU, labour market conditions for older people and the issue of active ageing.

To this end, a three-stage methodology is presented, with the first stage being a search focusing on the state of current research. The starting point is works examining changes in demographic behaviour. Theoretically, the topic is anchored by the approach of Malthus, who pointed out the problems associated with population growth. Other theoretical concepts are the theory of the population optimum or methodological concepts from geodemography and anthropogeography. The asymmetric nature of the population problem and the factors that lead to changes in demographic behavior are introduced. The literature review also responds to the issue of population policies, and the issue of active ageing in particular is key.

Secondly, an analysis of demographic developments is made, with an emphasis on the European Union. The analysis focuses on the phenomenon of population ageing. This process is set in a broader global context. On the basis of a literature search and theoretical-analytical anchoring, a reflection on European Union legislation in the context of improving the position of older people in various aspects of life, including in the context of equal treatment, active ageing and intergenerational solidarity, is also carried out. The ageing of the population is such a serious issue that the European Union is obliged to respond to it in its legislative and other (strategic) action. In the context of the currently very significant overlap between the originally purely economic nature of the European integration process and social (and political) integration, it is not only necessary to emphasise and essentially favour the economically active, i.e. employed or self-employed people, or other people of working age, but also to take into account the needs of older people, all the more so in the light of the deepening (and here presented) phenomenon of population ageing.

In this context, research questions can be asked about the extent to which EU legislation addresses the needs of older people, whether it effectively reflects their needs in all key areas, and in what areas legislative efforts can be strengthened to improve the position of older people in society and, more importantly, their quality of life.

This methodological approach is an approach that can be used as a basis for further research and identification of key issues related to the central issue of equal access to older persons.

1 LITERATURE REVIEW

Population has significantly influenced and influences the functioning of society, which is why considerable attention has been paid to the study of demographic processes in the past and is currently being paid. In particular, the growth of the world population is a very serious problem of the contemporary world. Humanity has begun to realize the seriousness of this problem since the beginning of the 1960s. At the same time, however, we can speak of a dichotomy of demographic development, since the European area is struggling with the opposite problem. More and more countries are currently recording deficit demographic growth.

Forecasting population development is one of the key problems of science both on a regional and global scale. In the regional (state) sphere, the forecast of population development is related to the planning and management of the development of almost all socio-economic areas (education and qualifications, labor force, housing issues, etc.). From a global perspective, population development is connected with issues of mineral and biological resources, ensuring nutrition for the population, maintaining ecological balance, etc. As mentioned, demographic development significantly affects the functioning of society, which is why much attention is paid to the study of demographic processes.

A number of authors mention fundamental changes in demographic behavior. They can be seen since the end of the last. The dynamics of population growth have decreased significantly, the changes are reflected in the fertility and mortality indicators. These changes change the demographic structure, the structure of families and households (e.g. Vlčková, Ivaničková, 2009).

Stula and Linz (2010) point out a turning point in the demographic development of Europe in particular. Low fertility leads to an increase in life expectancy. This significantly affects the demographic development of the European population. Hantrais (1999) deals with family size and the reduction of the family unit, which has become less institutionalized, which puts pressure on intergenerational relations. He argues that sociodemographic changes could have an impact on policy measures, but it is difficult to find convincing and consistent evidence to support the claim that policy has a determining effect on sociodemographic trends.

The current behavior of the population copies the behavior of the population that we previously observed in developed countries of Western Europe. An important moment of such behavior is a certain level of education, economic and social independence, independence of women, democratic environment, etc. Information about population processes and structures in current population development is extremely important for decision-making processes and planning activities. Demographic forecasts are the basis for thinking about the future development of society.

As part of a historical excursion, we present several authors who represented fundamental sources of demographic research. Francesco Sansovina (1521–1583) describes demographic phenomena. John Graunt (1620–1674) in his “Natural and Political Observations Made upon the Bills of Mortality” presents more modern forms of population registration. William Petty (1625–1687) popularized a new science that he called political arithmetic. Edmund Halley (1656–1742) compiled the first mortality tables and published an article on pensions, in which he presented an analysis of people’s ages at the time of death.

Johann Sussmilch (1707–1767), who was the first to formulate the so-called “laws of numbers” and compiled the first mortality tables for the entire population of Prussia. The 17th and 18th centuries were a period of flourishing of two theoretical schools of political economy – the mercantilists and the cameralists, who also created population theories in connection with their economic views. In their population theories, the mercantilists emphasized the economic, political and military advantages of a large and rapidly growing population. According to the mercantilists, more population meant more labor, and therefore more customers and increased prosperity for the ruler and merchants. They saw the positive aspects of a large population in increasing production for export and a large and strong army (Sirůček, 2007; Pavlík et al., 2009). Population growth should allow for an increase in national income and at the same time reduce the hourly wage of a worker to such an extent that it would encourage them to work longer. This would result in an increase in national income and a widening of the gap between national income and wage costs. This gap is supposed to be a source of growth in the wealth of society (Klufová, Poláková, 2010).

In the second half of the 18th century, more and more authors rejected mercantilist populationist doctrines and with them the idea of the advantages of a large and rapidly growing population and the obligation of the state to support it. Opinions that the size and speed of population growth depend on the sources of livelihood appeared more frequently. During this period, utopians came up with their theory, stating that when humanity reaches perfection, institutions such as the police, courts, property ownership or the family will not be needed. The progress of such a society would be in accordance with the number of inhabitants. Resources would be in common ownership and the limits of population growth would be determined by the functioning of a perfect society – automatically (Pavlík et al., 2009).

Thomas Robert Malthus (1766–1834) theoretically pointed out the problems associated with population growth and the availability of food resources. He concluded that if the population is not limited, it grows geometrically, while food only grows arithmetically. Social poverty and unemployment are therefore the result of too rapid human reproduction. He was criticized for this negative approach, especially because his theory did not take into account technological progress. Malthus summarized his theory in the following problem areas (Pastor, 2004). The size of the population converges to a limit set by the volume of food. Natural regulators such as shortages, hunger, diseases, premature mortality, etc. keep the population within these limits. Another area deals with the nature of declining soil fertility. He also deals with the ability of humans to reproduce, which exceeds the ability to provide sufficient sustenance. In the last area,

he compares the geometric growth of the population with the production of subsistence resources, which develops arithmetically. According to Malthus, it is impossible (natural laws do not allow it) to eliminate poverty in the "lower" strata of society.

According to Edwin Cannan's theory of population optimum from the end of the 19th century, it represents the number of inhabitants or their growth that can be considered the best and most suitable, possibly ideal, in a given territory under existing conditions and with regard to accepted economic, social, political, ecological and other criteria. (Pavlík et al., 2009, p. 88). Pavlík defines the theory as the rate of population that, given given resources, creates the highest domestic product per capita (Pavlík et al., 2009, p. 50), or as population growth that corresponds to the growth of the standard of living. If population growth is too fast, a demographic explosion occurs, followed by food shortages. The theory of population optimum has an economic framework in principle, and the population issue has always attracted many authors (Zimmermann, 1989; Willey, 2010; Daily, Ehrlich, Ehrlich 1994).

Spencer's theory is based on the assumption that fertility is a determining factor in population development and that high fertility leads to higher activity, because the more people there are, the greater the effort to survive. We come across the concerns of Darwinists: the fertility of the above-average intelligent part of the population is much lower than the fertility of the population with lower intelligence, i.e. the poorer classes. This leads to a decrease in the "quality" of the population (Peel, 2011).

A different methodological concept is represented by works on geodemography or anthropogeography. The main representative of this direction at the end of the 19th century was Friedrich Ratzel with his work *Anthropogeography* (1891). He focused on the distribution, number and density of the population. He understands the population as a set of plants or animals that are subject to the same natural laws. The influence of the natural environment affects the way of life and the population.

Malthus's population theory became the starting point for other unscientific population theories, such as the organic theory, the theory of quality populations, the theory of racism, and many other eclectic, reformist, and revisionist population theories. Malthus's work came into renewed focus after World War II, when the population boom was at its peak. In the 1960s, global population growth reached a maximum of 2%. Intellectuals at the Club of Rome warned of the threat of a population explosion. D. Meadows and his co-authors called in their report "The Limits to Growth" (1972) to slow down economic and population growth in order to prevent a catastrophic scenario. Among contemporary authors, we mention Gary Becker, the founder of the Chicago microeconomic school in demography. He analyzes the relationship between fertility and economic conditions using the economic apparatus. Unlike Malthus, he focuses not only on the number but also the "quality" of children that parents choose to have. His theory can explain why rising incomes can lead to falling fertility.

Malthusianism is a school of thought that follows Malthus. Previously, Malthusians and today's neo-Malthusians are not characterized by drawing attention to the possibility of global overpopulation, but prefer to solve societal problems through demographic measures, specifically by stopping population growth. However, reducing population growth alone will not eliminate poverty. Economic and cultural development can't be replaced by population restrictions.

Malthus's goal was to alleviate poverty, avoid misery and vice. Therefore, he recommended not supporting those who could not responsibly care for their children, and on the contrary, to increase the availability of food resources. However, Malthus knew that population pressure is the driving force of progress. The goal of neo-Malthusians is to stop population growth by all means, and above all by separating sexuality from fertility. The means of limiting the birth rate, which Malthus considered correct, neo-Malthusians reject as ineffective or limiting personal freedom. Malthus derived from the second basic postulate of his theory the necessity of subordinating one's behavior to morality and the development of the spirit. However, it is easier for neo-Malthusians to simply abolish Malthus's second postulate with its population effects (Pastor, 2004). Many works have also appeared that criticized Malthus' theory. (for example, Dokič, 2014, Unat, 2020, Smith, 2013 and others).

The population is not a static element, but is characterized by strong dynamics and changes. Changes relate mainly to the number, structure, spatial distribution and socio-economic changes. Changes in individual characteristics are usually interconnected and are a characteristic and very significant process of each population. Population dynamics include a large number of processes that manifest themselves differently at different geographical levels and are associated with specific problems. Population growth is related to ensuring its physical existence, in many regions in particular to the problem of ensuring a sufficient amount of food. At a lower level, population dynamics raises such issues as ensuring the required number of jobs, growth in national income, formation of a social structure, etc. Geographical differentiation is related to the main objective of our study, which is focused on the EU population and emphasizes the view on the position of older people and improving their position in society. Specifically, it focuses on the coordination of social security systems within the framework of the free movement of persons in the EU, on the conditions of employment and equal treatment of older people and the problem of active aging.

Current demographic trends are characterized by a change in the reproductive behavior of the population, characterized by a decrease in the birth rate, a change in family behavior and a shift in the value system. Similar conclusions were suggested by demographer Frank Notestein in his theory of demographic transition as early as the mid-20th century. This theory describes a possible transition from high birth and death rates to low birth and death rates as part of the economic transformation from an agrarian to an industrial country (Hagood, Stix, Notestein, 1941).

The population problem is a serious problem of the world and, together with the issue of international migration of the population, it significantly affects the quality of the environment and changes economic and social processes at the local level. However, the development of the world population is characterized by a dichotomy. The population in developed countries is stagnating and in some countries is decreasing, which leads to an aging population. In developing countries is the situation completely different.

Due to its asymmetry, solving the situation requires an individual approach and participation of the regions concerned and, in particular, individual governments. The population problem at the global level must be solved in a differentiated manner. In developing countries, it is necessary to solve the population explosion, which further brings with it the growth of poverty and illiteracy. Developed countries have a problem with the aging of the population and often a deficit population development, which further puts pressure on the economy and social services. The population problem affects economic processes, the environment, the problem of poverty and food shortages, as well as lack of energy and raw material.

The most important factors that caused population growth are the development of health care, ensuring sufficient nutrition for the population and a safe living and working environment. Another key factor was the increase in intensive agriculture due to the application of various scientific findings from the late 19th century and the early 20th century. A safe living and working environment have a positive effect on life expectancy. All of the above factors have a positive effect on the quality of life of a person and thus increase their average age. From a societal perspective, the increase in the age of the population is a great success, but from an economic and ecological perspective, concerns about the depletion of reserves and overpopulation of the planet are justified (Bloom, Canning, Fink, 2008).

Demographic behavior is a key indicator that significantly affects economic, political and social processes. Deviations at the local level are reflected globally, causing a number of interwoven activities. As a result of population aging in developed countries, the number of people in post-productive age is increasing, which causes an increasing burden on the economically active population. Low population growth in these countries significantly changes the age structure of the population. Market flexibility is changing the composition of the products and services offered, and due to current demographic developments, care for the elderly is becoming one of the most sought-after services. An undesirable express solution to increase the population is the influx of immigrants, which brings changes in culture and social tension.

A number of authors have addressed the above issues. Kabát considers the following as serious and specific attributes of demographic development in the first half of the 21st century:

decreasing population dynamics in developed countries, declining fertility and birth rates, increasing average age and the related aging of the population, migration of the population, the issue of AIDS and the spread of diseases (Kabát 2003, p. 1-5). Willekens focuses on the factors that cause demographic changes in different regions. These are family policy, economic reality, the impact of differences in education and attitudes towards marriage. New trends are restructuring the age composition of the population and reshaping the life processes of individuals and families. The impact on the organization of labor markets, fiscal policy, care for the elderly, migration flows and political changes can be radical (Willekens, 2014). EU countries have the lowest population growth rate, the lowest birth rate and the highest life expectancy. If these trends continue, the EU population will shrink, become older and have less population strength. The traditional measures are to increase the birth rate and increase immigration, assuming that this will increase population growth and rejuvenate the population. Díez-Nicolás (2004) demonstrates other ways to increase the dynamics of population growth, assuming that societies adopt the necessary changes to adapt to this new demographic situation.

In addition to the above-mentioned factors that led to changes in demographic behavior, population policies also played an important role in some EU countries (May, 2012, p. 137). Population policy, also referred to as family policy, can be perceived as part of the social, economic and also power policy of the state. We can say that through population policy, the state tries to effectively manage the demographic development of society. Population policy doesn't have a globally recognized definition, but nevertheless two general approaches apply to it. It is a set of public policies in a narrower sense that try to influence population growth or various demographic variables. In a broader sense, population policy includes the overall social, economic or other policy of the government that directly or indirectly influences demographic variables (Loužek, 2003, p. 49).

Population policies are therefore designed and implemented in the interest of the public good and aim to mitigate and, where possible, regulate population problems by adapting the size and age structure to the rights and needs of the people. These measures are defined as measures taken by public authorities to prevent, delay or address the imbalance between demographic change on the one hand and social, economic, environmental and political objectives on the other side.

Proposed policy interventions may target one or more components of demographic change. However, in industrialized and European countries, population policies are usually designed to address one demographic issue at a time. Policies are implemented through policy instruments, or interventions. These policy interventions are either direct, such as vaccination programs, or indirect, such as incentives to encourage couples to have more children. The implementation of population policies requires adequate political will as well as appropriate institutional arrangements, good coordination between different sectors, and effective monitoring and evaluation (May, 2015).

Population policy encompasses a much broader range of policies that directly and indirectly affect the population. G. F. Dumont (2006, p. 10) defines demographic policy as: "decisions and measures taken as a whole by public authorities that have demographic consequences." A policy that affects human population is, for example, the policy of providing health care. Similarly, prioritizing military spending over health care or taxing couples with children have demographic consequences (Dumont, 2006).

According to Roubíček (1997), population policy can be classified according to its objectives into quantitative and structural. The objective of quantitative policy is to regulate the development of the population. Structural policy has an impact on the structure of the population. We can also classify population policy according to the means used into stimulating and repressive policies. Mainly economic and psychological incentives are used to influence the behavior of the population. Population policy can be divided according to the subject of influence on natality and migration policy. The key factors for policy formulation are the perception of the demographic situation by political leaders and the expected consequences of various measures. States focus primarily on the questions of whether the current or expected development of demographic characteristics is beneficial or detrimental to society and how it is possible to

influence the development of these characteristics. If the state's intention is clear, it is possible to proceed with the adoption and application of population policy (Kalibová, 2002).

Although demographic trends in developed countries show similar developments, population policies are very often different. Experience from Western European countries defines four areas that, although they significantly interfere with indigenous cultures, are also attractive paths to higher living standards: children cease to be the workforce in the family and the costs of education and health care are borne by parents, women have access to employment and work is difficult to reconcile with upbringing, school attendance is promoted and primary and secondary education becomes compulsory, child labor is illegal, effective legal guarantees of property rights, legal enforcement of private contracts and the development of insurance and pension systems provide attractive and relatively safe alternatives for financial security in old age. The effectiveness of family planning programs in reducing birth rates remains a controversial issue. Even in developing countries that did not have government programs promoting family planning. A decline in birth rates has been noted as a side effect of economic and social development. Therefore, the impact of family planning programs is unclear. (Leisinger, 2011).

The decline in the dynamics of demographic growth in the EU represents a clear threat to maintaining the viability of the territory. Population aging in the absence of migration would create practically insoluble problems and probably a loss of geopolitical position. The issues associated with the growing number of elderly people, which is the focus of our study, are also urgent. These are primarily the areas of coordination of social security systems within the framework of the free movement of persons in the EU, the conditions of labor markets for older people and the issue of active aging.

Pascual-Saez, Cantarero-Prieto and Pires Manso (2020) examined the combination of demographic and economic variables in selected developed countries. They found that longevity has a significant impact on savings. Population aging is one of the most important issues affecting policymakers and EU countries face it in a multidimensional context. The authors drew the following conclusions: aggregate savings have shown a certain tendency to decline in recent years, policymakers can support savings and investment at the same time. The last conclusion is the finding that there are obstacles to the movement of human capital and at the same time the consequences need to be seen (Pascual-Saez, et al., 2020). Kočanová, Kováč, Serzhanov and Buleca, J. (2023) examined the aging process and relations between EU member states in 2009–2019. These countries are analyzed according to several indicators: health status, labor market conditions and financial security. The emphasis is on the 55+ age group, as it is a disadvantaged age group in the job application process. It is an important aspect of the public finance system. Strupczewski (Strupczewski, 2024) focused on the issue of aging society and related economic problems. Prskawetz and Lindh (Prskawetz, Lindh, 2007) examined the relationship between demographic changes and economic growth in the EU. Other authors focused on this topic directly in the Central Europe and Baltic region (Khachatryan, Nepytyaliuk, Pasichnyi, Nasibova, Tabenska, 2023). Other authors also focused on demographic developments in the EU. They focused on the impact of changes in the age structure on the expenditure and revenue of state budgets. The authors found that demographic changes (such as population aging and shrinking labor force size) affect not only public finances and social security but also income distribution (Dolls, Doorley, Paulus, 2019). Other studies point out the dangers of a rapid increase in the elderly population, especially during times of crisis.

Our article also responds to the issue of active aging. For example, Foster and Walker (2021) map the development of active aging responses to demographic change. They contrast this concept with the notion of successful aging and other terms such as “ageing well”. They assess how the population has not engaged in a comprehensive approach to active aging and that the concept of active aging still plays an important role in understanding the population and responses to aging. Successful aging is a theory that describes the aging process and the expected activities and behaviors that older people should engage in to age successfully. In more detail, in a synthesis of existing research by Teater and Chonody (2020), twelve main themes were found, ranging from the importance of social relationships and interactions to a “good” death. The findings suggested that older people do not define successful aging as strictly as previously

reported. Age and the aging process from the perspective of older people provide future directions for theory development and further research. According to Jayawardhana, Jayathilaka, Nimnadi, Anuththara, Karadanaarachchi, Galappaththi, Dharmasena (2023), the impact of ageing on the economies of EU countries is relatively small so far, thanks to policy planning and cultural approaches that perceive older people as a potential asset. However, they emphasize that in the near future, this idea will need to be developed and that increasing life expectancy will be perceived as a long-term investment. It will be necessary to find new ways to involve older people in order to avoid overburdening the economically active population.

EU countries face a variety of challenges caused by population ageing, linked to many aspects of the economy, such as economic globalisation, international trade, economic growth, the labour force, pension system development, protection of the rights of older people, capital accumulation and savings. Demographic change therefore poses a policy challenge in EU countries. The European Commission's 2018 Ageing Report points out that the age structure of the EU population will change significantly in the coming decades. Population changes depend on assumptions regarding fertility rates, life expectancy and migration. This new situation has important implications for labour force projections, future GDP growth and other social factors, such as longer schooling, access to early retirement or pension reforms. The challenges posed by demographic change focus on the labour market, reforms of social protection systems, healthcare and long-term care measures. The main policy directions are therefore: supporting demographic renewal, increasing employment, increasing productivity and economic performance by investing in education and research, welcoming and integrating migrants, and ensuring sustainable public finances to guarantee adequate pensions, healthcare and long-term care (European Commission, 2018).

The latest 2024 report on population ageing provides detailed economic and budgetary information and projections for the EU Member States and Norway up to 2070. It presents the process of population ageing and its economic consequences and related budgetary challenges. Such pressures are already evident in many countries and are expected to accelerate as large baby boomers retire, life expectancy increases and fertility rates remain low (European Commission, 2024).

2 GLOBAL AND EUROPEAN DYNAMICS OF POPULATION AGEING: DEMOGRAPHIC TRENDS AND SOCIOECONOMIC IMPLICATIONS

Population decline and the associated problems of population ageing are one of the major contemporary issues that require urgent attention because of their current, but above all future, impact on individual countries. Population ageing is one of the fundamental features of current population development, with its future, probably irreversible, impact. The intensity and importance of this process is significant on a global scale, especially in the last 100 years. Population ageing is thus causally linked to the demographic transition and its completion in the more economically developed countries of the world. The economic and social consequences of ageing perhaps need no special mention. The time is fast approaching when the ratio of pensioners to children will reverse. It will be a time when social customs, habits and norms will have to change. This is one of the main reasons why special attention needs to be paid to this phenomenon. (Bleha, Vaño, 2007, s. 62-80)

The increase in the proportion of the population in older age will lead to many undesirable macroeconomic problems. (Bloom, et al., 2015) Older people do not work as much as young and middle-aged adults, which means that an economy populated mainly by such people will tend to create less output (on a per-person basis) than an economy with a higher proportion of individuals at prime working ages. Cross-country differences aside, workforce participation typically peaks at about age 40 years, and falls to less than 50% by age 65 years for men and by age 55 years for women. This decrease might be partly offset by a workforce that is effectively enlarged by increased investments in education, training, and health. Additionally, declines in fertility can result in an increased number of women working because of reduced childcare responsibilities, which will contribute to economic growth

Another factor is that, consumption accounts for a higher proportion of income in older adults than for those at the prime working ages. Theoretically, as the older share of the population rises, average savings rates will tend to fall, potentially leading to a scarcity of investment capital. However, the negative relation between the proportion of the population aged more than 65 years and the savings rate is not nearly as clear as might be expected. Likewise, the growing proportion of older people tends to increase demands on pension systems. This finding is especially relevant when effective pension coverage is high and when a system aims to guarantee a minimum level of protection, irrespective of earnings history, as for most high-income countries. Population ageing introduces new difficulties for the fiscal integrity of public and private pension systems, such as a low share of workers contributing to the system and longer periods of benefit receipt associated with increased longevity. In low-income and middle-income countries the difficulties tend to be different – some are encountering population ageing before they have secured comprehensive social security coverage and before they have the resources to support large cohorts of retired people

The link between population ageing and pension costs is not as direct as generally claimed. Both high-income countries and low- and middle-income countries often have strong incentives to retire early. In low- and middle-income countries with high levels of informal employment and low levels of social security, pension systems are dominated by expensive and reform-resistant civil service systems. In some countries, pension liabilities have assumed enormous proportions - for example, in Brazil, public spending on pensions is equivalent to 13% of national gross domestic product, with similar proportions spent in Italy and France. However, in other countries, such as the UK, public sector pension spending as a share of GDP is falling, partly attributable to increased privatisation and delayed retirement. The experience of examining different pension policy reforms shows that no one system is best and that reforms should be tailored to each country individually.

Also, various diseases and disabilities in older adults represent a substantial loss of national production. The supply of a workforce is depleted by mortality and morbidity, which are concentrated factors in older people. Capital is also depleted, because of the diversion of savings to spending on health and long-term care. Calculations based on a macroeconomic model developed by WHO suggest that sizeable costs are associated with noncommunicable diseases, which predominate in older adults. However, large cross-country differences in the age-specific prevalence of most noncommunicable diseases suggest that the effects of ageing can be modified.

Last but not least, older people place a large burden on health and long-term care systems, especially in high-income countries, and contribute reduced revenue to their support. The positive correlation between health-care expenditure and the proportion of elderly people in a population is partly because countries with older populations tend to have higher incomes and thus can spend more on health than younger populations. But even with controls set for income, this association still holds. Increased health-care spending at older ages is largely driven by much higher outlays in the final years of life, with substantial heterogeneity. (Bloom, et al., 2015, p. 652)

Before the 20th century, few people lived to a ripe old age to be called senior citizens. The revolution in modern medical technology that took place at the beginning of the 20th century resulted in the cure of many deadly diseases and a reduction in mortality rates in most countries of the world. The average life expectancy of the population in many countries is therefore increasing rapidly, and this automatically increases the number of elderly citizens. Many countries in the developing world have experienced a change from situations of high fertility and high mortality to low fertility and low mortality, a process called the demographic transition. In tracing demographic history, the growth of the elderly population is closely linked to the rate of a country's demographic transition. The confluence of reduced fertility and improved health and longevity has led to an increasing number and proportion of the elderly population worldwide. The decline in the proportion of young people and the decline in mortality, especially at older ages, is leading to an increase in the number of older citizens in the population structure. These changes, coupled with ageing, are leading to an increasing number of older citizens. The steady increase in life expectancy at older ages will be a general trend in most countries of the world. (Ismail, et al., 2021, p. 2452). It is widely believed that longevity rates are likely to have a large impact on life-

cycle behaviour, i.e. healthier people who live longer have a stronger incentive to invest in skills development, generate more investment or save more. However, the increasing dependency of older people tends to be jointly assessed with longer life expectancy. (Pascual-Saez, et al., 2020, p. 300)

EU countries reached a high socio-economic level even before they faced an ageing population. Already Modigliani and Brumberg (1954) pointed out that, according to the life cycle, savings are negative for the pre- and post-reproductive groups of the population, and an increasing dependency ratio reduces national savings, which has a significant impact on economic growth. In addition, investment in human capital is also affected. As a consequence, population changes have a significant impact on education and health spending. (Pascual-Saez, et al., 2020, p. 292)

In many regions of the world populations have grown older and fertility rates have declined to very low levels, leading to simultaneously shrinking and ageing populations. Globally, people above 65 years old are the fastest-growing segments of the population and in 2019, for the first time in human history, they outnumbered children younger than 5 years old. Population change, and especially population increase, has always been central to debates over sustainability. For example, the UN Agenda 2030 was mostly discussed in the context of a rapidly growing global population, focusing on the strategies needed to achieve the sustainable development goals (SDGs) in view of the ever-increasing population pressures. (Jarzebski, et al., 2021)

Global aging is today's reality and the UN has identified several major issues related to aging trajectories: (Khan. 2019, p. 755)

- Population ageing is unprecedented, ie, the 21st century will witness rapid ageing at a pace not seen before.
- Population ageing is pervasive, ie, a global phenomenon that will affect everyone. Countries that started the planning process late will have less time to adjust.
- Population ageing is enduring, ie, there will not be a return to the younger populations that were so familiar to our ancestors.

Thus, the 21st century can be described as the first historical milestone in human history when the world will no longer be young. There will be drastic changes in many aspects of our lives, including socio-demographic changes, financial preparedness and attitudes to healthcare in old age. Older people will thus inevitably face enormous risks and challenges in later life.

Population ageing has been occurring since the 1950s, but its severity only began to become apparent globally in the 1990s. In the late 20th and early 21st centuries, major technological and technical advances have brought about fundamental changes in lifestyles and, consequently, in the reproductive behaviour of the population. The possibility of a diversity of lifestyles has led to the disappearance of the traditions of the so-called classical family and reproductive values. The family has taken on a new form, where its members have greater individuality than in the traditional family of the past.

Between now and 2030, every country will experience population ageing - a trend that is both pronounced and historically unprecedented. Over the past six decades, countries of the world had experienced only a slight increase in the share of people aged 60 years and older, from 8% to 10%. But in the next four decades, this group is expected to rise to 22% of the total population-a jump from 800 million to 2 billion people. Evidence suggests that cohorts entering older age now are healthier than previous ones. However, progress has been very uneven, as indicated by the wide gaps in population health (measured by life expectancy) between the worst (Sierra Leone) and best (Japan) performing countries, now standing at a difference of 36 years for life expectancy at birth and 15 years for life expectancy at age 60 years. Population ageing poses challenges for countries' economies, and the health of older populations is of concern. (Bloom, et al., 2015, p. 649)

By 2050, a quarter of the population will be over 60 years in almost every continent in the world except Africa. There will be huge variation in terms of absolute size and relative rates across these countries. In today's world, 65 years of age looks like the new 40 as people feel physically

strong and also have confidence in their health status. In recent years, researchers have become interested in exploring populations aged 80+ years, ie, the oldest old group. There is a growing trend for this oldest-old cohort in the years 1950 to 2050 and by 2050, there will be more than 350 million in the 80+ population globally with most of them living in less developed countries. A little over 50 million people aged 80+ will be seen in Europe. A complete opposite scenario is indicated by the percentage rate. Our analysis shows that the percentage rate will be higher in developed countries and be the highest in Europe. The trend analysis shows that the 80+ populations follow an exponential growth rate. This means that the increase may be beyond our imagination. By 2050, Japan will have the highest percentage (about 15.6%) of the 80+ population in the world followed by China and Hong Kong (15.6%). Japan is already known as a “super ageing” society. This can be explained by the fact that Japanese population size has been affected by long-term low fertility as well as having no immigration policy, whereas China and Hong Kong's oldest-old age groups are likely to be affected by the one-child policy and outward migration. Also, by this time, the United States and United Kingdom will have approximately 11.8% and 9.5%, respectively, of 80+ people in their populations. The lower rate in these countries is due to their sustainable immigration policies that will give them both a longer time to adjust their ageing society programmes. (Khan, 2019, p. 755)

Current research demonstrates that population ageing is not merely a demographic or economic issue, but also encompasses significant social and legislative dimensions that are closely linked to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The SDGs are officially defined by the United Nations within the framework of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, which was adopted by all UN Member States in 2015 (United Nations, 2015). The SDG-related literature provides a systematic framework for analysing the impacts of population ageing on the economy, health, social cohesion, and the environment (Wang et al., 2024; Šimková, 2021).

For example, SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-Being), SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), and SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities) enable demographic change to be linked to specific policies targeting older populations, thereby creating space for a multidimensional assessment of sustainable development (WHO, 2020).

As noted, for example, by Dvouletý (2025), in the context of the broader implementation of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and increasing life expectancy, it is essential to understand the factors that shape the well-being and quality of life of older populations. His key findings highlight the importance of well-being determinants related to individuals' economic circumstances, such as employment or self-employment in the post-retirement phase, household financial conditions, and the interactions between economic variables and respondents' health status. In particular, economic activity—namely engagement in paid work after retirement—has a positive effect on overall well-being. A positive association was also identified between self-perceived health and overall well-being. Overall well-being tends to decline with increasing age, while no significant differences were observed between genders, despite expected disparities in life expectancy. The author concludes that health status plays a crucial role in maintaining quality of life in later life, with the interaction between economic and health-related factors being particularly significant. The findings further suggest that merely increasing the statutory retirement age, without creating appropriate conditions for maintaining physical fitness, labour market flexibility, and access to suitable forms of employment, may not lead to the desired outcomes in terms of the well-being of older populations. From a public policy perspective, the study also points to the need for a comprehensive approach to population ageing that integrates labour market policies, healthcare, and social security systems.

Interdisciplinary research at the intersection of law and social sciences also indicates that legislative measures—such as flexible pension systems, labour-market regulation, and the support of social services—can be evaluated through the SDG framework (de Teixeira et al., 2024). In this context, the SDGs function as a bridge between theoretical research and practical policymaking, facilitating the identification of effective instruments for promoting sustainable and inclusive solutions to challenges associated with population ageing (Shevelkova et al., 2023).

Another important dimension is economic sustainability. Studies show that green finance and investment in sustainable projects can mitigate the negative economic impacts of population

ageing by fostering innovation, employment opportunities, and sustainable technologies (Wang et al., 2024; Ma, 2023). This approach aligns with SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth), SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), thereby linking the economic, environmental, and demographic dimensions of sustainable development.

It is also evident that the impacts of population ageing are not homogeneous, but vary considerably depending on regional characteristics, levels of economic development, and demographic structures (Nicolini & Roig, 2023). The SDGs provide a unified framework that enables the comparison of regional policies and the identification of areas requiring targeted legislative and economic support. For instance, densely populated and economically advanced regions require measures aimed at increasing productivity and labour-market adaptation, whereas less developed regions may benefit more from strengthening healthcare and social services.

It can therefore be concluded that integrating SDG-related literature into the theoretical framework of population-ageing research enables the interconnected economic, social, and environmental dimensions to be addressed simultaneously and provides empirically grounded support for policymaking that is sustainable, inclusive, and sensitive to regional differentiation (Jarzębski, Elmquist, Gasparatos et al., 2021; Shevelkova et al., 2023).

Currently, older people have greater health and long-term care needs than younger people, leading to increased expenditure. They are also less likely to work if they are unhealthy, and could impose an economic burden on families and society (Bloom, et al., 2015)

Human societies will need to develop mechanisms and social practices to minimize or mitigate the social isolation that is common among the elderly in the future, especially in communities that lack social capital. The lack of social capital reflects the fact that the typical family structure provides less intergenerational support than in the past and, more recently, studies have shown that persistent or recurrent periods of social separation are associated with significant health risks. Social innovations are needed to enable individuals to age in the same communities in which they work and live in mid-, early- and late-life. The relatively new concepts of 'age-friendly community' and 'age-friendly society' assume that older people will remain active agents in their own care. (Sander, et al. 2014, p. 186)

In 2020, 9% of the global population was above 65 years old, accounting for 728 million people. This population is projected to increase more than twofold, reaching 1.55 billion in 2050 and accounting to 16% of global population, at medium fertility rates. People above 80 years old accounted for 143 million in 2019, and are expected to reach 426 million in 2050 and account for nearly 60% of the elderly population, increasing particularly fast in high-income countries. However, there are major regional discrepancies in current and future patterns of ageing, with Europe expected to remain the most aged society in 2050, Asia experiencing large increases in aged population (especially in China), and most countries in Africa having a mostly young population. Regardless of these trends, in both affluent and less affluent regions, older women generally greatly outnumber older men, with the oldest age groups in some regions being completely female. (Jarzebski, et al., 2021, p. 2)

The issue of ageing is not yet a global problem, but concerns mainly the developed countries of the world. On the other hand, it is a well-known fact that the process of population ageing in developing countries, which will peak in a few decades, will be more dramatic than the ageing that is currently taking place in the developed world. In the developed countries, ageing is currently caused by, on the one hand, the extension of human life and, on the other, low birth rates. This trend is the result of a number of circumstances linked to the modernisation of society, which has caused fertility and birth rates to fall. Improvements in medical assistance have resulted in longer life expectancy and better health of the population. Advances in science have increased life expectancy, which is the most significant reason for the ageing of the population.

As few children are born, the proportion of the elderly and old in the population is increasing. In developed countries, the ageing process has now advanced to such an extent that it has become one of the most serious social problems. The ageing of the population is not just a prognostic issue,

but a serious economic problem worldwide, with fewer and fewer citizens in active employment contributing to the state budgets and, conversely, a steady increase in the number of recipients of state pensions, while the strain on health and social services is also increasing. As a result, the overall functioning of the economy may be threatened, and major changes are therefore needed in social, health and pension provision for the population, as well as in employment policy. Ageing affects the life cycle of individuals and their family behaviour. The complexity of the situation in the developed countries is primarily that, while population growth in developing countries will decline as society progresses, in the developed countries external resources will have to be sought to improve the situation in the coming years and reproductive behaviour will have to change over a period of several decades, based on a change in the value system of the population. (Vaňo, 2001, s. 35)

Muffels (1998, pp. 285-302) speaks of a "double generation of the old" in the context of demographic ageing, that is, an increase in the proportion of old and "elderly" persons, which will be all the greater the greater the decline in the number of young people relative to the number of old people. In most cases, the determination of the age of old age is significantly influenced by the fact of when retirement eligibility is triggered, which varies in different social security systems. According to Jurčová (2002), population ageing refers to changes in the age structure caused by an increase in the proportion of old people in the population. It defines the terms:

- Ageing from below - ageing of the population as a result of decreasing fertility (decreasing relative representation of the child component of the population),
- Ageing from above - ageing of the population as a result of an increase in the human lifespan (the relative representation of the older component of the population is increasing).

It draws attention to the importance of distinguishing between absolute and relative ageing:

- Absolute ageing - an increase in the number of older people in the population, due to declining mortality rates and increasing life expectancy.
- Relative ageing - increase in the proportion of the population of older age groups as a result of the increase in their numbers, the decrease in the number of the population of pre-reproductive, possibly reproductive age.

The very process of population ageing, to which we can reduce the evolution of the age structure, is essentially based on the relationship between two basic demographic processes - fertility and mortality. This relationship is determined, according to Rabušić (2002), by the result of the rationalization of people's approach to the basic questions of life:

- People limit childbearing because they want to raise quality offspring, and consequently low population growths of children lead to an increase in the proportion of the old population.
- The unprecedented standard of living in modern industrial and post-industrial societies and the concept of healthy lifestyles have atypically increased the quality of life, which - together with the development of medical knowledge and technology - has been reflected in a gradual and significant improvement in mortality rates.

Around the world, populations are getting older. This phenomenon, so far typical only of developed countries, is slowly becoming a reality in less developed countries as well. By 2050, almost 1.2 billion of the 1.5 billion people over 65 will be in what we now call less developed countries. A phenomenon of this magnitude will have a huge impact on the level of health and socio-economic development of countries across the planet.

In terms of the long-term demographic development of the population in the context of population ageing, it is the fertility and fertility indicators that are used for such projections, which have a long-term trend development. The cumulative fertility - fertility index - means the average number of children a woman gives birth to in her lifetime. This is given as the level needed to maintain population stability and is a value of 2.1 children. It is therefore logical that a population with a high fertility rate is likely to have a smaller proportion of old people and vice versa.

Change in the age-structure of human populations reflects decrease in average human fertility rates to ≤ 1.5 births per woman and continuing increase in human lifespan. In very few countries (for example Vietnam), age-structural change has led to decreases in youth and total dependency while the size of the working age population and the standard of living has increased. In many more countries (for example Italy), the total dependency ratio is increasing as the working age population is shrinking, and long-standing social conventions, such as designated pension age and poor acceptance of women in the workforce, present obstacles to adaptive change. (Sander, et al. 2014, p. 185)

The reduction in mortality rates, especially neonatal and child mortality, is also an important factor, thanks to improved and accessible public health services and a number of programmes to reduce morbidity. Last but not least, the ageing of the population is also due to an increase in life expectancy. In some countries, it even doubled during the 20th century. The increase was more significant between 1900 and 1950, when several Western countries saw increases of up to 20 years. Virtually all countries show a continuous increase, with some exceptions in Latin America and Africa, mainly due to the impact of increased mortality caused by HIV/AIDS or other major diseases.

According to the UN report, global life expectancy has increased from 47 years (calculated for the period 1950-1955) to 68 years in 2005-2010. According to the report by then UN Secretary-General Pan Ki-mun, people are living longer mainly due to better nutrition and hygiene, as well as advances in health care, especially vaccines and drugs against communicable infectious diseases and parasites. In particular, the number of deaths among children and younger people has decreased. However, older people are still dying from non-communicable chronic and degenerative diseases such as cancer, diabetes, respiratory and heart disease. The report therefore calls on governments to seek preventive measures to combat these phenomena. These include combating obesity, physical inactivity, alcohol and tobacco use. Overall, the number of deaths after the age of 60 has risen from 26% of the population between 1950 and 1955 to 54% between 2005 and 2010. (Čajka, Kazanský, 2014)

All these demographic changes are causing an ageing population, huge changes in the age structure of both developed and developing countries. It also raises the issue of 'depopulation', a phenomenon that has received insufficient attention to date. This is the reduction in the total population in some countries.

One of the causes of increasing depopulation is the current trends in mortality. A World Health Organization (WHO) report (Mathers, et al., 2005) in the context of global mortality trend research points to the increasing prevalence of disease-related mortality even in some technologically advanced countries. At the same time, there are increasing disparities in life expectancy and mortality between the developed and developing world. Life expectancy data from the Western world are increasingly diverging from those of the developing world, particularly in Africa.

Population ageing in low-income and middle-income countries is likely to aggravate existing strains on formal health systems. It will also magnify the needs for long-term care, as traditional family-based approaches become less feasible because of declines in fertility and socioeconomic changes. Most low-income and middle-income countries have long had young populations, so their health systems are attuned to issues that predominantly affect the young and working-age populations. As populations age, the distribution of health disorders changes, with an increased prevalence of cancer, fractures, cardiovascular diseases, depression, and dementia and many comorbidities that need a wide range of potentially interacting treatments. Complicating this situation, the epidemiological transition is also driven by risks accumulated during the life course, when not successfully counteracting risks in early life and young adulthood will mean an older adult population with possibly increased levels of ill health and disability. (Bloom, et al., 2015, p. 652)

3 SELECTED LEGISLATIVE (AND RELATED) STRATEGIC ACTIVITIES OF THE EUROPEAN UNION CONCERNING OLDER PERSONS

Population ageing, a major demographic shift affecting all Member States of the European Union, constitutes one of the important challenges to which the European Union is compelled to respond through both its legislative and strategic activities. In this context, European union legislation is required to reflect the need for the systematic improvement of the status of older persons in various aspects of human life-not only in the area of social security, which is naturally associated with older persons due to its content and purpose, but also in the context of equal treatment, active ageing, and intergenerational solidarity.

The improvement of the status of older persons and their protection falls within the scope of social policy. Social policy has not constituted a more significant role within the framework of the European Union (respectively the European Economic Community and the European Communities) and its legislation throughout all stages of its existence. The European Union was originally focused primarily on economic integration, particularly through the establishment of the common market and the support of economic cooperation among Member States. This economic orientation dominated the initial development.⁵

Over time, however, the European Union began to increasingly focus on social matters. This shift towards social matters can be seen as characteristic particularly at the turn of the 1980s and 1990s, when the Treaty of Maastricht (1992) enshrined a broad social dimension of the activities of the European Union, including the safeguarding of labour rights and the improvement of living conditions. Currently, the European Union is already focused on a range of crucial factors related to social policy. These include, for example, ensuring equality, social protection, protection of vulnerable groups, and many others (Ondrášek, 2024, p. 114). The support of older persons thus also falls within this framework.

From the perspective of European Union law, respectively its binding legislation, the inclusion of age as a protected ground of discrimination under Council Directive 2000/78/EC of 27 November 2000, establishing a general framework for equal treatment in employment and occupation, is undoubtedly of particular significance. This legislative act serves as the foundation for combating age discrimination in the workplace across the Member States (see further below). In addition to binding legislation, the European Commission and other institutions of European Union also focus on the formulation of strategic documents and initiatives aimed at contributing to a comprehensive improvement in the quality of life of older persons. A key milestone in this regard is the 2021 Green Paper on Ageing, which sets out as its goal “to launch a broad policy debate on ageing to discuss options on how to anticipate and respond to the challenges and opportunities it brings.” The document generally underlines, in particular, the necessity of lifelong learning, access to healthcare and social services, as well as the preservation of healthy and active ageing (see further below). It is also appropriate to highlight the existence of the European Commission’s communication – Union of Equality: Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021–2030, which, although primarily focused on persons with disabilities, also has a fundamental impact on the lives of older persons due to the frequent intersection of older age and health-related limitations.

If we take a closer look at the legislative activity of the European Union in relation to the aspect of the prohibition of discrimination against older persons in their working life, it has already been outlined that this issue, given also the coherent European Union legislation, is of high importance and represents a prime example of the European Union's positive approach to improving the living conditions of older persons. This aspect should not, however, be viewed solely in connection with the European union legislation aimed at supporting and improving the

⁵ However, it cannot be overlooked that even in the 1950s, certain steps were taken to strengthen social policy (particularly in relation to employment); for example, the Treaty establishing the European Coal and Steel Community, which was adopted in 1951, supported the improvement of working conditions of employees and the enhancement of their standard of living. Furthermore, the Treaty of Rome, adopted in 1957, established the European Social Fund (cf. Ondrášek et al., 2022, p. 100).

status of older persons, but also as one of the important topics within European labour law as such. This is further evident from the case law of the Court of Justice of the European Union (hereinafter referred to as "CJEU"), which, in relation to the prohibition of age discrimination, predominantly concerns the area of employment and occupation (Ombudsman).⁶

The importance of the aspect of combating age discrimination (generally, not just in relation to employment and occupation) also stems from the fact that it is enshrined in the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (hereinafter referred to as "TFEU"), specifically in Article 19 thereof⁷, as well as in the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (hereinafter referred to as "CFR"), specifically in Article 21 thereof.⁸ The aforementioned Article 21 of the CFR serves as a fundamental basis and ground, as it prohibits discrimination, inter alia, on the grounds of age (in a general sense, not solely in relation to employment). Both of the aforementioned provisions aim to combat discrimination on various socio-biological grounds, meaning not only on the grounds of age, but also on the grounds of sex or ethnic origin.⁹

In light of the above, as well as the related secondary legislation of the European Union, it is clear that the European Union fully recognizes that discriminatory conduct can significantly and negatively impact social factors and exacerbate social tensions, but also undermine the economic stability of the Member States as well as the European union as a whole (compare Forejtová, 2014). However, it is necessary to point out the negative aspect of the currently applicable and effective anti-discrimination secondary legislation of the European Union. It is highly fragmented and, importantly, does not cover all protected grounds across the various areas of life. As such, secondary legislation does not adequately react to the aforementioned Article 21 of the CFR and fails to fully utilize its potential to set limits on unwanted discriminatory conduct within the area of the European Union.

If we focus further specifically on the area of equal treatment in the performance of employment by older persons (and the associated prohibition of discrimination), it is reflected in the secondary legislation of the European Union. In this regard, an important directive has been adopted, which significantly impacts the national legal systems of the Member States¹⁰, namely the aforementioned Council Directive 2000/78/EC.

⁶ At this point, it is appropriate to mention in connection with the case law of the CJEU that it considers the prohibition of age discrimination as a general principle of European Union law; compare the Judgment of the CJEU of November 22, 2005, in case C-144/04, Werner Mangold v. Rüdiger Helm.

⁷ Article 19(1) of the TFEU states: "*Without prejudice to other provisions of the Treaties and within the limits of the powers conferred by them upon the Union, the Council, acting unanimously in accordance with a special legislative procedure and after obtaining the consent of the European Parliament, may take appropriate action to combat discrimination based on sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation.*" Article 19(2) of the TFEU states: "*By way of derogation from paragraph 1, the European Parliament and the Council, acting in accordance with the ordinary legislative procedure, may adopt the basic principles of Union incentive measures, excluding any harmonisation of the laws and regulations of the Member States, to support action taken by the Member States in order to contribute to the achievement of the objectives referred to in paragraph 1.*"

⁸ Article 21(1) of the CFR states: "*Any discrimination based on any ground such as sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation shall be prohibited.*" Article 21(2) of the CFR states: "*Within the scope of application of the Treaty establishing the European Community and of the Treaty on European Union, and without prejudice to the special provisions of those, any discrimination on grounds of nationality shall be prohibited.*"

⁹ The list of discriminatory grounds under Article 21 of the CFR is demonstrative and includes a broader range of concrete grounds. In contrast, Article 19 of the TFEU provides a legally binding list of discriminatory grounds more concise. In both cases, however, age is considered a discriminatory ground. Legal literature concludes that the primary law of the European Union regulates six basic grounds of discrimination that are used to combat discrimination: sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age, and sexual orientation (Compare Koldinská, 2017, p. 80).

¹⁰ For example, within the context of the Czech legal system, the aforementioned directive is primarily reflected in Act No. 198/2009 Coll., on equal treatment and legal means of protection against discrimination (see § 1(1) and footnote No. 1 of the Act No. 198/2009 Coll.).

The objective of Directive 2000/78/EC, as outlined in its Article 1, is to establish a general framework for combating discrimination (both direct and indirect) in employment and occupation, with age being one of the protected grounds under this directive. The term "principle of equal treatment" is understood by the directive as the absence of any direct or indirect discrimination.¹¹ Therefore, while discrimination based on age is prohibited in the sense of this directive (thus safeguarding the position of older persons in employment and occupation), its Article 6 (which specifically addresses age as a discriminatory ground) allows Member States to provide that certain differences in treatment based on age do not constitute discrimination if (i) they are objectively and reasonably justified by a legitimate aim, particularly related to employment policy, labour market and vocational training objectives, and cumulatively if (ii) the means to achieve these objectives are appropriate and necessary. As with any other directive, Directive 2000/78/EC is binding on Member States in terms of the result to be achieved, while the choice of form and means to achieve the objectives of the directive is left to the Member States (Kudláčková, 2011, pp. 119–120). In this regard, Member States must ensure the enforceability of the provisions adopted in accordance with the transposition of the directive within their national legislation; without real enforceability (particularly the establishment of national legal sanctions for violations of individual provisions), the legal norm lacks practical applicability.¹²

A significant disadvantage of any anti-discrimination legislation, including Directive 2000/78/EC, is the fact that individual life situations are not always identical and may, from a general perspective, differ in minor ways, but upon closer inspection, these differences can be crucial and relevant for assessing potential discriminatory treatment. "Mere" provisions of legislation cannot provide a clear-cut answer as to which cases of differential treatment are justified and which are not, especially due to the general nature of legal norms. Therefore, judicial case law constitutes a significant, even crucial, role, including the case law of the CJEU, which in many cases provides resolution through answers to preliminary questions from the national courts of the Member States, including those concerning the (non-)discriminatory treatment of older persons and their protection.

In connection with age discrimination, it is appropriate to highlight the Judgment of the CJEU dated 5 July 2017 in Case C-190/16, *Werner Fries v Lufthansa CityLine GmbH*,¹³ which illustrates and demonstrates the specific manner in which the CJEU examines, assesses, and decides whether a particular legal provision is in conflict with the prohibition of discrimination or not.

Werner Fries was employed as a pilot with Lufthansa airline until the end of 2013, in connection with commercial air transport.¹⁴ In October 2013, Mr. Fries reached the age of 65, and as of 31 December 2013, his employment contract with Lufthansa ended, as he reached the age at which, in accordance with the applicable collective agreement, he was entitled to receive a regular pension under the public pension system. However, Lufthansa ceased employing him as of 31 October 2013, due to the provisions of Regulation No. 1178/2011, which stipulate¹⁵ that a pilot who has reached the age of 65 may not perform the profession of a pilot in commercial air transport. The Federal Labor Court in Germany, which was considering the case at the national level, submitted several preliminary questions, but the key preliminary question regarding

¹¹ Within the meaning of Article 2(1) of this directive.

¹² For example, Act No. 198/2009 Coll. provides in its § 10 that persons affected by discriminatory conduct can seek judicial remedies, including a cessation of discrimination, removal of the consequences of discriminatory actions, appropriate compensation, or, if these remedies are insufficient and the discrimination was more severe, the right to claim non-pecuniary damages (thus sanctioning the perpetrator of the discriminatory conduct).

¹³ Its subject was a request for a preliminary ruling submitted under Article 267 TFEU by a decision of the Bundesarbeitsgericht (Federal Labour Court, Germany) of 27 January 2016, which was received by the CJEU on 5 April 2016, in the case of *Werner Fries v. Lufthansa CityLine GmbH*.

¹⁴ This refers to the transportation of passengers, cargo, or mail for remuneration or hire, as defined in point FCL.010 of Annex I to Commission Regulation (EU) No. 1178/2011 of 3 November 2011 laying down technical requirements and administrative procedures related to civil aviation aircrew pursuant to Regulation (EC) No. 216/2008 of the European Parliament and of the Council.

¹⁵ See point FCL.065(b) of Annex I to Regulation No. 1178/2011.

potential age discrimination is whether point FCL.065(b) of Annex I to Regulation No. 1178/2011 (i.e., the age limit for performing the pilot profession in commercial air transport) is compatible with the prohibition of age discrimination set out in Article 21(1) of the CFR.

In the reasoning of the judgment, the CJEU initially recalled that its established case law states that the principle of non-discrimination requires that comparable situations not be treated differently and that different situations not be treated the same, unless such treatment is objectively justified.¹⁶ The aforementioned can be considered as the basic concept of non-discriminatory conduct. In assessing whether a legal provision is discriminatory or not, it is necessary to apply the proportionality test and examine three aspects of the legal regulation (measure) in question, namely its (i) suitability, (ii) necessity, and (iii) proportionality. In the case under consideration, the CJEU concluded that the legal regulation in question meets all three criteria of the proportionality test. The criterion of suitability is met by the objective of preventing aviation accidents through the control of pilots' competence and physical fitness, to ensure that human error is not the cause of accidents, as pilots' fitness declines with age.¹⁷ The maximum age limit is a suitable measure to achieve the aforementioned objective. The adoption of the measure that only individuals with the required physical abilities are authorized to be pilots is necessary in the context of the case under consideration in order to minimize the risks of failure due to human error. Regarding the aspect of proportionality, the CJEU concluded that in order to maintain an appropriate level of civil aviation safety in Europe, it is proportionate to establish an age limit for the profession of a pilot in commercial air transport, with the age limit of 65 years being sufficiently advanced in relation to the measure under review.¹⁸

Considering the non-legislative activities related to older persons carried out at the European Union level, it has already been mentioned that the Green Paper on Ageing, adopted in 2021, contributes to the comprehensive improvement of the quality of life of older persons. Green Papers as such are documents issued by the European Commission to initiate a discussion on specific topics at the European Union level. They serve as a call to relevant persons or bodies to participate in consultations and discussions on proposals contained in the Green Papers. Green Papers can serve as a precursor to subsequently adopted European union legislation (Publications Office of the European Union, 2022).

The Green Paper on Ageing is particularly significant (and relevant to this contribution) primarily due to its broad content, as it addresses a variety of key areas of life of older persons. First and foremost, it focuses on establishing the foundations-factors that shape the future and influence health and well-being. In this regard, two specific political concepts are emphasized: healthy and active ageing (a healthy lifestyle throughout life, including dietary and consumption habits, as well as physical and social activities), and lifelong learning (investment in skills, competencies, or knowledge throughout life, including consideration of territorial differences in access to education).

Healthy and active ageing is construed as being promoted through the systematic support of healthy lifestyles across the entire life course, its *conditio sine qua non* being a sustained emphasis on consumption patterns, dietary habits, and the level of individuals' physical and social activity. Such an approach contributes to the mitigation of the continuously increasing risks associated with obesity, diabetes, and other non-communicable diseases. The promotion of healthy and active ageing exerts a positive influence on labour market functioning, employment rates, and the sustainability of social protection systems within the European Union, thereby also supporting overall economic productivity.

The Green Paper on Ageing emphasises that, while healthy and active ageing is, in principle, a matter of individual choice and personal responsibility and is therefore *a priori* not directly

¹⁶ For example, the Judgment of the CJEU of March 1, 2011, in Case C-236/09, *Association belge des Consommateurs Test-Achats ASBL and others v. Conseil des ministres*, paragraph 28.

¹⁷ Compare the Judgment of the CJEU of September 13, 2011, in Case C-447/09, *Reinhard Prigge and others v. Deutsche Lufthansa AG*.

¹⁸ Compare the Judgment of the CJEU of January 12, 2010, in Case C-341/08, *Domnica Petersen v. Berufungsausschuss für Zahnärzte für den Bezirk Westfalen-Lippe*.

contingent upon national or Union-level public policies, it is nonetheless significantly shaped by the environmental, social, and institutional contexts in which individuals operate. Accordingly, public authorities may play a substantial enabling role in fostering conditions conducive to healthy and active ageing. The Green Paper further recognises that health policy remains primarily within the competence of the Member States and thus generally falls outside the direct regulatory scope of the European Union. This delimitation of competences, however, does not preclude the Union from supporting and complementing national measures, *inter alia* through targeted instruments such as the “EU4Health” programme, including initiatives aimed at cancer prevention, dementia care, mental health promotion, the encouragement of healthy nutrition and dietary practices, and the promotion of regular physical activity.

A further critical dimension of the challenges associated with population ageing concerns lifelong learning, understood as sustained investment in the acquisition and development of knowledge, skills, and competences throughout the life course. Lifelong learning proves to be most effective when initiated at an early stage and maintained continuously. Ongoing investment in education positively affects individuals’ employability and labour market participation, contributes to mental well-being, and may delay the onset of dementia as well as mitigate age-related cognitive decline. Nevertheless, a persistent structural concern remains the high proportion of young people who leave formal education prematurely and experience significant deficiencies in fundamental skills, including literacy, numeracy, and scientific competence. This challenge is compounded by the fact that approximately one fifth of young people in Europe lack basic digital skills, with individuals from socially disadvantaged backgrounds being disproportionately affected.

The Green Paper on Ageing further focuses on optimising the use of working life potential (including investments aimed at supporting the regional development of less developed regions), with particular emphasis placed on ensuring a high level of labour market participation—*inter alia* by combating discrimination and enabling the full utilisation of the potential of persons belonging to ethnic or racial minorities—and on extending working lives. High labour market participation and longer working lives are identified as key factors that may alleviate the challenges faced by ageing societies resulting from a declining working-age population. The Green Paper on Ageing also addresses issues of productivity, innovation, and business opportunities, highlighting the crucial importance of adequate investment in research and development, as well as the role of effective public administration and an efficient judicial system in this regard. Also not overlooked is solidarity¹⁹ and the consequences of older persons retiring, including ensuring their financial situation in light of their lower income from pensions²⁰ (and the related need for a well-functioning pension system) or efforts to keep these persons active and engaged in intergenerational knowledge sharing or volunteer work.

The Green Paper on Ageing is, in our opinion, an absolutely appropriate tool for setting goals and efforts in the area of improvement of the quality of life of older persons, and several of its essential factors can be appreciated. First and foremost, it is a document issued by the European Commission, the main executive body of the European Union, whose activities have a key impact on life within the European Union's territory. The Green Paper on Ageing is comprehensive in terms of improving the lives of older persons, covering a wide range of areas connected to the lives of older persons (from a healthy lifestyle to, for example, the involvement of retirees in social life or their financial security after the end of their working life). From our perspective, a very important factor is that the Green Paper on Ageing does not focus exclusively on already attained older (loosely, pensionable) age but emphasizes the importance of preventing the negative consequences of aging, especially through an active lifestyle and learning during the life stages that precede the final stages of our lives.

From a legal perspective, it is important to note that the Green Paper on Ageing (like any other Green Paper) is not a legal act and therefore does not create any legal effects. The goals and

¹⁹ Both mandatory and voluntary solidarity (for more details to these terms, see Tomeš, Bočková, 2017, p. 9 and 10).

²⁰ In the sense of old-age pension (for more details to this term, see Voříšek, 2013, p. 145 and 146).

ideas outlined in the Green Paper on Ageing are relevant and certainly appropriate, even necessary in many respects. These goals and ideas may be regarded as truly significant simply because they have been formulated in a formal document by the European Commission. However, the key lies in their realization through binding legislation, namely, in the light of European Union law, through secondary legislation. In this regard, a key obstacle arises: the Green Paper on Ageing has not yet triggered a "legislative avalanche" and has not delivered the desired outcome—the adoption of specific legislation to support older persons in the areas it addresses.

CONCLUSION

Population ageing poses some daunting major macroeconomic challenges, but there are many options to address them. These options include behavioural responses by individuals, such as higher rates of savings and educational attainment in anticipation of a longer life expectancy, and increased participation of women, immigrants and older people in the labour force. Businesses can respond by adjusting human resource practices and adopting technological innovations that meet the needs of older workers. Policy responses may include delaying the retirement age or finding incentives for delayed retirement; redesigning pension funding; slowing the growth of benefits; and investing in education to expand the effective workforce. These myriad responses can interact and reinforce each other, with longer working lives supporting higher income taxes and revenues, improving both private and public ability to provide health and long-term care. Moreover, the earlier policy and institutional reforms are initiated, the smoother the path of macroeconomic adjustment to an aging population (Bloom, et al., 2015).

Population ageing is a success story of the development process, but it also poses various challenges for older people themselves. Various researchers believe that population ageing has become a demographic reality that deserves serious attention. The effects of an ageing population are generally related to changes in the family, the migration of young people to cities, the need for support and care, the need to pay attention to health problems, the need for financial security and housing problems. All these impacts are not only related to the impact of ageing in the developed world, but affect all countries worldwide.

An ageing population presents many challenges and ignoring them could undermine the potential benefits and opportunities that longer life can bring. Although life expectancy extension is a global trend, the impact is not evenly distributed around the world. Increasing health care to meet the growing demand for care for the elderly would be a major challenge on the one hand, and financing the cost of care at the individual and national level would be a major challenge on the other. Many countries in the world are not prepared for this, but developing countries are likely to face even greater challenges than developed countries in the coming years. Ageing should not be seen as a problem because of unmanageable size, care and cost. There are also huge opportunities for ageing as older people increasingly contribute to society as workers, volunteers, taxpayers and carers. Future research could focus on the preventative side of illness to reduce the financial burden and improve wellbeing in later life. (Khan. 2019)

Population ageing represents a major demographic change for the European Union, requiring a comprehensive legislative and strategic response. As shown in particular by the non-legislative initiatives of the European Union institutions, the European Union is fully aware of the importance of protecting the rights of older people and their active participation in all aspects of life, including the working environment, social security and intergenerational solidarity. The development of legislation, such as Council Directive 2000/78/EC, which protects persons against age discrimination in employment and occupation, and the related case law of the CJEU, which provides practical answers to the assessment of specific cases of (non-)discriminatory practices on grounds of age and which cannot be ignored because of its importance, and non-legislative documents such as the Green Paper on Ageing, are some steps towards achieving these objectives.

Unfortunately, there are still major gaps that need to be addressed for the future. It has been pointed out that the European Union's secondary legislation on age discrimination is highly relevant to improving the lives of older people, but that in its current state (as with other discriminatory grounds) it does not cover all the worthwhile areas of life. These shortcomings are

underlined and highlighted by the Green Paper on Ageing, which sets out a number of important and relevant issues of immediate relevance to older people that need to be addressed, ideally by adopting appropriate secondary legislation. However, this has not yet happened.

As such, Green Papers - as already mentioned - are documents issued by the European Commission with the purpose of launching a debate on specific topics at the European Union level, they are an invitation to the relevant bodies to participate in consultations and discussions on the proposals put forward in Green Papers, i.e. they are often the germ of subsequently adopted binding legislation of the European Union. However, these are not in themselves sufficient to bring about a generalised change of approach to specific issues; this needs to be followed up by the adoption of secondary EU legislation, whether in the form of a regulation or a directive, as legislative instruments which the Member States are obliged to implement (in the case of directives) in their legal order within a specified implementation period or to apply directly (in the case of regulations). It is not possible to improve the living conditions and rights of older people by limiting oneself to identifying problems through Green Papers; only rational legislative action is capable of improving their daily lives and positively promoting the realisation of their rights and legitimate interests in the areas identified.

In this context, *lege ferenda* can be proposed for the adoption of appropriate (harmonised or unified) secondary legislation at EU level in favour of senior citizens' activities, whereby, for example, older persons or persons of pensionable age who participate in (accredited) training courses or volunteer activities could receive a tax credit or a direct financial contribution, etc. At the level of (European) labour law, there could be an obligation for employers to adapt working conditions for older workers, e.g. in the form of part-time work, working from home or flexible working hours without the risk of discrimination, or an obligation for larger employers, i.e. employers with a certain larger (minimum) number of employees (or turnover, etc.) to provide for a minimum number of employees.) to employ older people on a compulsory basis, or to be able to 'buy their way out' of this obligation by making a regular contribution to the Intergenerational Solidarity Fund, a fund which could pay for programmes to support older people and their involvement in the active ageing process (i.e. training courses, volunteering activities, etc.).

Overall, it can be concluded that the European Union has made progress in protecting the rights of the elderly, but to achieve a truly strong and desirable position, it is essential to continue legislative action in a meaningful way. Emphasis on lifelong learning, healthy ageing and ensuring the economic and social stability of older people must be placed on a par with the economic and political priorities of the European Union in order to improve the quality of life of this demographic group across the European Union.

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